

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN PRIMARY CLASSES IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract. *This article discusses information technology, the importance of information technology in improving the effectiveness of education and the order of use of modern information technology in primary school students.*

Keywords: *information, technology, pedagogy, education, reform, education, science*

Topic statement. The mechanisms for improving the methodology of teaching information technology in primary classes are being put into practice in the conditions of digitalization in higher education institutions of the world. In the conditions of digitalization of educational processes, the systematic work is being carried out to improve the methodology of information technology teaching in primary classes, to ensure becoming in harmony with the culture of countries, and to implement large-scale projects on teaching the subject of information technology.

The acceleration of the growth of science, technology, and the information technology in it has brought frequent updates to the development of scientific and technical information. It is known that the method of data and information transmission needs to be updated and improved. In the process of primary education, it is desirable to implement such teaching methods, as a result of which they teach students to read and think independently, to work creatively with information, to guide students to their own thinking, to develop the ability of effective working, increase their interest in studying and independent learning, cultivate a critical approach to their work, and develop the skills of quick adaptation to changing production conditions.[1]

In the primary education system, new pedagogical technologies, including information technologies, greatly contribute to the development of the motivation to learn. Lessons organized on the basis of information technologies should meet the needs of the student according to organizational methods and methods of conducting. Because such lessons are closer to the child's psyche. Achieving the goal based on arousing students' interest, intention and desire to learn educational materials is motivation, and this is the internal rapprochement of the teacher and students. It is emphasized in scientific studies that information and communication technologies have a great impact on the development of students' theoretical, creative and reflexive thinking. The figurative expression of this or that event or process in the memory of students enriches the educational material and helps to assimilate it scientifically.

A scientific and methodical works aimed at eliminating the problems encountered in the way of computerization of processes at all stages of education, the creation and implementation of new information and pedagogical technologies that allow the world's rapidly developing scale of information, their assimilation and processing. work, the need for electronic textbooks and pedagogical software tools from various general education subjects is increasing day by day.

The word information comes from the Latin word "informatio", which means "to explain, to explain".

The word "technology" in the phrase "information technologies" comes from the Latin "thexnos" - art, craft, field, and "logos" - science. That is, technology means different ways of performing a task.

Information technologies are a set of methods and tools for collecting, storing, transmitting, and processing information.[2]

The main conditions for achieving the intended goals in the primary school educational process: in the use of advanced pedagogical and information technologies from modern educational methods, the use of the latest educational tools, and the improvement of the effectiveness of this process is to ensure that primary school teachers have high methodical professional training.

Implementation of information technologies in the educational system opens wide opportunities for the use of modern teaching methods in the educational process.

Information technology has become such an integral part of the structure of society that it is no longer just a technological process, but rather a social process. The state's economic power, international influence, and the level of development of a democratic institution are increasingly dependent on the research of information technologies. Information has become an extremely important and unlimited resource of mankind. This requires increasing our information in the national segment of the Internet, regardless of the field. A great place is allocated to Internet technologies in the process of teaching and learning. Such technologies are facilitating the educational process, making it possible to access teaching programs, study guides, e-textbooks and journals, which in turn provide users with scientific schoolwork. It is very important for students to have a critical approach to the information they get from the Internet and expand their worldview based on its useful sources, expand their worldview based on biased sources, and be able to deny biased information.

Using a set of different didactic materials for primary school students, it is possible to prepare mixed computer programs that include demonstration-exercise, control-exercise and test modules. The use of rich and varied materials on grammar-orthographic topics given in three options for current learning and generalized repetition of the rules of science will give good results.

It is possible to prepare and use electronic educational guides in the 1st grade class. In it, it is possible to provide a variety of interesting visual and audio material, such as the sound-letter analysis of the word, the structure of the syllables of the word, the study of some orphograms. Bright pictures, strange and interesting tasks help to increase interest in the mother tongue in young students, allow them to get acquainted with the educational material in the form of a game, provide wide opportunities for self-control and educational reflection. Differentiation of the educational process according to this manual is achieved by selecting tasks of different levels of complexity. When developing thematic planning for literacy training, electronic topics and sections related to planning can be included. In the development of the lesson plan, it is necessary to develop the stages of the lesson in which it is appropriate to use the computer for frontal, individual and group work.

"Game problems" programs can be prepared and used in mathematics classes. A variety of materials are provided on many of the topics learned in the primary school. A variety of tasks at different levels of complexity help to develop the perceptive and creative abilities of each student [3].

The use of computer-animated slides in solving problems (tasks) increases the interest of the lesson. Their advantage is that you can return to the beginning of the issue at any time, stop at its individual parts, talk with students, and listen to their opinions. Slide films with animated problems can be used for movement in primary classes. To create such slides, you can use animated pictures from the Internet.

Determining the availability of opportunities to use computer technologies in primary education is one of the most important indicators of using such technologies in the educational process. Taking into account the achievements in this field, it should be noted that the use of computer technology in the following aspects will be effective in the processes of the general activity of the educational institution. Prospective directions of informatization of primary education indicate the use of modern telecommunication tools and network information technologies. When using such tools, general education schools and higher education institutions open up new opportunities to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. The computer expands educational resources, that is, the possibility of using various multimedia textbooks, e-books, etc. is becoming widespread. Taking this into account, today's implementation of information technologies into practice puts new demands on the educational system, as well as informatization in the field of education in primary classes, and of the environment of educational activities from each educational institution. The new direction of educational development brought to the field the educational system organized with the help of informational educational multimedia tools. The ways and means of consistently and step-by-step solutions to problems in the personnel training and education system, in the field of educational work, are specified in the above-mentioned state documents.

Game methods, interactive methods, modular technologies, non-traditional forms of lessons, interdisciplinary integration can be used in the lessons of primary classes. All these methods require children to work independently, to be able to express their opinion freely, and to think broadly.

The professional potential and level of education of a primary school teacher, knowledge of modern educational methods are important in improving the quality of education. Unfortunately, some teachers still do not sufficiently use information and communication technologies and multimedia tools for the traditional teaching system in the course of the lesson, as well as the methodical recommendations given on the educational system sites. Therefore, the special attention is being paid to the study of educational methods and tools used in the teaching process today, modern forms of organizing the teaching process.

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